

Participants Consent Form

I have been given sufficient time to consider whether to participate in this study, and I understand participation is voluntary and that I may withdraw from the study at any time during the survey. I agree to participate in this study and acknowledge that my responses will be anonymous and kept strictly confidential.

- Yes.
- No.

Section 1: 3D printing technology implementation challenges

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statement about the challenges of implementing 3D printing technology in the construction industry in your country?

Strongly Disagree Disagree Somewhat Disagree Neither Agree nor Disagree Somewhat Agree Agree Strongly Agree

The current workforce lacks adequate technical skills to effectively adopt 3D printing technology.

There is insufficient access to training for workers on how to operate 3D printing technology.

Resistance among workers presents a significant challenge to reskilling efforts for 3D printing adoption.

Existing 3D printing technology is not yet mature enough for application in large-scale construction projects.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Somewhat Disagree Neither Agree nor Disagree Somewhat Agree Agree Strongly Agree

3D printing materials are not consistently available in many regions.

Some business owners face difficulties accessing digital systems that facilitate 3D printing in construction.

Integrating 3D printing technology into construction projects will lead to significant logistical challenges.

The procurement process for 3D printing materials and equipment differs significantly from traditional construction.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Somewhat Disagree Neither Agree nor Disagree Somewhat Agree Agree Strongly Agree

Lack of project experience will make it difficult to predict project timelines.

The initial investment cost for a 3D printing construction business is prohibitively high.

The cost of 3D printer maintenance is a significant challenge.

The cost of printable materials and logistics for transporting printed structures is high.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Somewhat Disagree Neither Agree nor Disagree Somewhat Agree Agree Strongly Agree

There is a lack of industry-wide awareness regarding the adoption of 3D printing technology in construction.

Customer demand for 3D-printed buildings is currently insufficient to drive widespread adoption.

Coordination between various stakeholders is more complex in 3D printing construction projects.

Existing regulations don't adequately support the use of 3D printing in construction.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Somewhat Disagree Neither Agree nor Disagree Somewhat Agree Agree Strongly Agree

Great job on completing the first section! To confirm you're still engaged, please select 'Disagree' for this statement.

Section 2: Supply chain management and 3D printing technology integration

In your opinion, how significant are the following procedures within the construction supply chain?

	Not important at all	Slightly important	Somewhat important	Moderately important	Very important	Extremely important	
Production planning	<input type="radio"/>						
Payment Process	<input type="radio"/>						
Transportation	<input type="radio"/>						

Not important at all Slightly important Somewhat important Moderately important Very important Extremely important Absolut

Handling material and production storage

In your opinion, how significant are the following factors when selecting suppliers for your projects?

Not important at all Slightly important Somewhat important Moderately important Very important Extremely important Absolut

The supplier provides a competitive price.

The supplier has better quality service.

The supplier helps to simplify the construction process.

The supplier has a simple ordering process.

In your opinion, how significantly do the following obstacles impact your procurement goals?

	Not important at all	Slightly important	Somewhat important	Moderately important	Very important	Extremely important	A
Delivery order delays.	<input type="radio"/>	€					
Unexpected increase of procurement costs.	<input type="radio"/>						
Unstable quality of the supplied materials.	<input type="radio"/>						
Negative environmental impact during the procurement process.	<input type="radio"/>						

In your opinion, how significantly do the following barriers affect construction supply chain management?

	Not important at all	Slightly important	Somewhat important	Moderately important	Very important	Extremely important	A
The project management team lacks commitment.	<input type="radio"/>						

Not important at all Slightly important Somewhat important Moderately important Very important Extremely important A

Project stakeholders have a poor understanding of supply chain concept.

The project lacks appropriate information technology.

The strategic benefits remains unclear.

To what extent do you agree or disagree regarding the following statements on integrating supply chain management with 3D printing technology?

Strongly Disagree Disagree Somewhat Disagree Neither Agree nor Disagree Somewhat Agree Agree Strongly Agree

3D printing technology will help to reduce the impacts of material supply fluctuations in construction projects.

The integration of 3D printing encourages innovation in construction supply chain management.

Integrating 3D printing with supply chain management can reduce material waste and improve sustainability.

3D printing will help the construction industry reduce costs by less material and time consumption.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Somewhat Disagree Neither Agree nor Disagree Somewhat Agree Strongly Agree

3D printing construction technology will increase the supply chain efficiency of construction projects.

You're almost done with Section 2! To confirm you're still engaged, please select 'Disagree' for this statement.

If 3D printing is introduced to your projects, where do you think the most critical challenge will arise in the supply chain? (Please tick one)?

- Technology accessibility and utilisation
- Transportation/Logistics
- Material procurement
- Skill of the employees

Other, please specify:

What do you think are the three biggest challenges in managing the supply chain for 3D concrete printing? Please describe them.

Section 3: 3D concrete printing project supply chain management

Have you ever been or are currently involved in a 3D printing project?

- Yes
- No

What type of 3D printing projects do you usually construct?

- On-site printing: print the structure on project site directly.
- Off-site printing: print structure in factory, then transport prefabricated structure to project site for assembling.

What do you think the safety stock level should be for 3D concrete printing materials?

- 0 - 49.9% of total demand
- 50% - 74.9% of total demand
- 75% - 99.9% of total demand
- Equal or above 100% of total demand

What is the most common method used to transport materials to your warehouse?

- In-house fleet
- Third-party logistics
- Suppliers' transportation
- Other, please specify:

Compared to traditional construction material sourcing, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following challenges in sourcing 3D printing materials?

Strongly Disagree Disagree Somewhat Disagree Neither Agree nor Disagree Somewhat Agree Agree Strongly Agree

The technical quality and suitability of materials are crucial in 3D printing projects.

The supplier's production capacity for 3D printing materials influences my supplier selection.

The delivery method and logistics of 3D printing materials impact project efficiency.

A strong buyer-supplier relationship is an important factor in selecting a 3D printing material supplier.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Somewhat Disagree Neither Agree nor Disagree Somewhat Agree Agree Strongly Agree

The suppliers' reputation significantly affects my decision when sourcing 3D printing materials.

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following cost-related challenges of 3D concrete printing materials in your projects?

Strongly Disagree Disagree Somewhat Disagree Neither Agree nor Disagree Somewhat Agree Agree Strongly Agree

The small number of suppliers is a reason for the high cost of 3D printing materials.

Variations in 3D printing material demand will lead to a significant increase in costs.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Somewhat Disagree Neither Agree nor Disagree Somewhat Agree Agree Strongly Agree

The quality and compatibility requirements for 3D printing materials can increase the costs.

Unexpected charges during procurement increase the costs of 3D printing material sourcing.

The lack of standardization in 3D printing materials makes it challenging to control costs.

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following challenges related to the transportation of 3D printing materials for your projects?

Strongly Disagree Disagree Somewhat Disagree Neither Agree nor Disagree Somewhat Agree Agree Strongly Agree

Logistics costs of 3D printing materials significantly impact the overall cost-effectiveness of the project.

Delivery speed of 3D printing materials directly influences project efficiency.

Real-time updates on logistics information for 3D printing materials are essential for effective project management.

Regulatory requirements for transporting 3D printing construction materials affect logistics efficiency.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Somewhat Disagree Neither Agree nor Disagree Somewhat Agree Agree Strongly Agree

I plan to implement strategies to enhance transportation safety and minimize environmental impact.

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following challenges related to the transportation of 3D-printed structures for your projects?

Strongly Disagree Disagree Somewhat Disagree Neither Agree nor Disagree Somewhat Agree Agree Strongly Agree

Logistics costs of 3D printed structures significantly impact the overall cost-effectiveness of the project.

Delivery speed of 3D printed structures directly influences project efficiency.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Somewhat Disagree Neither Agree nor Disagree Somewhat Agree Agree Strongly Agree

Real-time updates on logistics information for 3D printed structures are essential for effective project management.

Regulatory requirements for transporting 3D printed structures affect logistics efficiency.

I plan to implement strategies to enhance transportation safety and minimize environmental impact.

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following challenges to the storage of 3D printing materials in your projects?

Strongly Disagree Disagree Somewhat Disagree Neither Agree nor Disagree Somewhat Agree Agree Strongly Agree

Ensuring that materials remain printable is a big challenge.

Having an adequate supply of materials is essential for 3D printing construction activities.

Having a security plan to prevent 3D printing material loss is necessary.

Protecting stock 3D printing materials is essential to prevent contamination.

Keeping the material warehouse close to 3D printing project sites improves efficiency.

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following challenges to the use of 3D printing materials?

Strongly Disagree Disagree Somewhat Disagree Neither Agree nor Disagree Somewhat Agree Strongly Agree

The quality of 3D printing materials greatly affects the quality of printed structures.

3D printing speed is an important factor that affects construction efficiency.

I need real-time material tracking during the 3D printing process.

I make sure to choose materials that are perfectly compatible with my 3D printer to prevent concrete blockage.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Somewhat Disagree Neither Agree nor Disagree Somewhat Agree Agree Strongly Agree

I need a waste management plan to minimise environmental impact.

Great job on completing Section 3! To confirm you're still engaged, please select 'Disagree' for this statement.

Section 4: Demographic information

Where is your primary work location or operational base?
(Please specify the city and country.)

What is the business type that you are working with?

- Developer
- Contractor

- Supplier
- Consultancy
- Academic institution
- Other, please specify:

What is your current role in the construction sector?

- Project manager
- Site manager
- Engineer/Digital manager
- Procurement manager/Quantity surveyor/Cost manager
- Material manufacturer or supplier
- Consultant
- Researcher
- Other, please specify:

How many years have you been working in the construction sector?

- Less than 1 year
- 1 year to less than 3 years
- 3 years to less than 5 years
- 5 years to 10 years
- More than 10 years

Are you interested in participating in a follow-up interview for around 30 minutes on the same subject of this questionnaire survey?

Yes, contact email:

No

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